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Firm Characteristics and Earnings Smoothing among Quoted Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study had successfully undertaken an investigation that empirically x-rayed the effect of firm characteristics on earnings smoothing among quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria. Specifically, the study evaluates the effect of firm size on earnings smoothing of quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria. Ascertain the extent to which firm leverage affect earnings smoothing of quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria. Examine the effect of firm age on earnings smoothing of quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria and investigate the effect of managerial ownership on earnings smoothing of quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study utilized secondary data extracted from annual reports and accounts of the ten sampled banks with specific interest on firm age, firm size, firm leverage and managerial ownership as they affect earnings smoothing. The data mining was for ten years from 2013 to 2022 and robust analytical technique of random effect test was employed for the analysis. The result provided the assurance that forms our conclusion that firm size and firm age are the two veritable firm characteristics that are indispensably determinant of earnings smoothing as measured by loan loss provision of deposit money banks listed on Nigeria exchange limited.

Keywords: Firm Size, Leverage, Firm Age, Managerial Ownership, Firm Characteristics

INTRODUCTION

Accounting earnings are the most extensively used measure of firm financial performance. Given that financial reporting standards and accounting policies provide managers of the firm with considerable opportunities for manipulating earnings, it is not surprising that the growing attention in accounting literature has been devoted to understanding the determinants of earnings management. The collapse of once profitable and prominent corporations (Enron, Xerox, WorldCom, HealthSouth, Tyco, Waste Management, Rite Aid and Sunbeam, to mention a few) because of financial reporting fraud further reveals the harmful nature of Earning Management. Healy and Wahlen (1999) define earnings management (EM) as what happens “when managers use judgment in financial reporting and in structuring transactions to alter financial reports to either mislead some stakeholders about the underlying economic performance of the company or to influence contractual outcomes that depend on reported accounting numbers.” Flexibility in financial reporting (accounting methods and treatments) presents managers with opportunities by which they can manage earnings, which may either positively or negatively affect the quality of reported earnings and their value in the decision-making process. Research further confirms managerial motives in Earning Management; for example, increasing executive stock-based compensation, avoiding debt covenants violation, meeting or exceeding stock analysts’ forecasts, and earnings smoothing (Kliestik et al., 2021).

Sensitivity analysis indicates that we cannot rule out selections bias as a potential alternative explanation for earning smoothing. Companies with high profit may pump their financial reports more than companies with low income to smooth their earnings. Shareholders will face loss because of income volatility. Smoothing of earning can be either artificial or real smoothing involve decision that affect cash flow and firm value, having cost that are obvious. Artificial smoothing is also known as accounting smoothing because it is achieved through accounting choice and differs from real smoothing, which is also called transactional smoothing, as it occurs through real transactions with parties external to the company. From this distinction, it follows that artificial smoothing cannot be implemented by managing changes in payment time (real time) (Massimo Ceechi, 2021). Income smoothing is a special form of earnings management under which the managers manipulate earning to make earnings look less variable over time. Firm investors report smooth earnings to have higher market valuation, since investors are found to assign higher weights firms reporting consistent earnings (Massimo Ceechi, 2021).

Firm characteristics play an important role in explaining the quality of earnings as they affect a firm's internal and external decision making and restrains managers from manipulating the accounting information. Firm characteristics are defined as firm internal environment that are composed of demographic and managerial variables which in turn comprises part of the firm's internal environment (Mutende et al, 2017). These firms attribute which includes leverage, age, size, and profitability can be controllable or uncontrollable and always used for internal or external decision and could be prone to mangers manipulation. Proofs have emerged that the choice of firm and its in-house governance mechanism affect firm's financial reporting quality especially with respect to monitoring variable such as institutional shareholding and board meeting (Musa Adeiza Farouk et al 2019). Against this backdrop, the present study deems it plausible in this area to examine the effect of firm characteristic and earning smoothing of quoted deposit money bank in Nigeria, and how it affect these variables such as: firm age, firm size, firm leverage and managerial ownership. To the best knowledge of the researcher, much has been done base on availability of related literature.

Statement of the Problem

Statistics from resent financial reports reveal a worrying trend that a significant percentage of manufacturing companies engage in income smoothing practice that compromise the transparency and accuracy of financial information. Inaccurate information hinders effective decision- making, potentially leading to bad investment and lower confidence in financial market. To promote transparency, accountability and sustainable economic growth, it is essential to address income smoothing in Banks and manufacturing sector in Nigeria. Income smoothing can be detriment to investors in making decisions based on fundamental analysis. Therefore, the review of income smoothing needs further investigation (Welly Chandra et al 2023).

The study is motivated by two fundamental gaps in the literature. First, the effect of firm characteristics and earnings smoothing has been less investigated in the literature in Nigeria. This means that the issue of earnings management through income/earnings smoothing is partly understood and practiced in Nigeria as it is still needed more study. Secondly, most of prior studies on effect of firm characteristics were purely directed to firm performance leaving its effect with earnings smoothing unexplored thereby creating room for more studies. In prior literature especially in the context of Nigeria quoted firms, various proxies have been used to measure earnings management: fraud cases, restatements, abnormal accruals and discretionary accruals. However, discretionary accrual models dominate earnings management literature which is consistent with prior studies who mentioned that the analysis of earnings management mostly focuses on management's use of discretionary accruals. Other employed measures include earnings or income smoothing, earnings restatements or reported fraud cases which have been scarcely employed in prior literature. It is in line with this rare measure of earnings smoothing that we carry out this study and apply the loan loss provision as an absolute value of discretionary accruals to measure earnings smoothing

Review of Related Literature

Firm Characteristic

Firm characteristic is defined as the behavior patterns of companies' operation which enable them to achieve their objectives throughout the period of existence. Company characteristics vary from one business entity to another. They can be determined based on the relevant information disclosed on financial statement for a particular accounting period (Kaguri A. W. 2013). They are of the view that firms that are able to align firm attributes with the environmental characteristics perform better than the other firms (Shehu and Bello 2013).

Previous study revealed that firm characteristic attributes can greatly affect entrepreneurial development, therefore firm characteristic play a major role in determining not just performance but also play vital role in entrepreneurship development across the firm. Company characteristic have identified to have substantial role in explaining quality of financial reporting. A firm characteristic refers to those variables of motivations which are moderately stuck to firm at various levels and across time. Shehu and Belo (2013) posited that firm structural characteristics are vital component of companies' characteristics which refer to as character that deal with structure of a company's mostly distinctively to the company. According to Musa Adeiza Farouk et al (2019) firm characteristic could be controllable and uncontrollable, internal or external to the firm decision and can be prone to manager manipulation. Firm characteristics include market-related structure, market capitalization, cash holdings, book-to capitalization, cash holding book to market ratio.

Firm Size

Firm size has been variously defined in the literature to refer to the total assets, scale of operations and number of employees among others. According to Kenny Adekpo Soyeme et al (2019) firm size is an attribute that affect financial reporting quality. A large firm is expected to have well-structured accounting and internal control department and should be able to afford the services of professionals who are expected to enhance the financial reporting process (Chalaki et al 2012). The size of the firm can be measured in many ways, e.g., through turnover, paid-up-capital, capital employed, total assets, net sales, etc. The measure to be selected precisely depends upon the nature of the problem at hand. That is the concept of firm size describes how large or small a company is and can be measured by its total assets or by its total capitalization. Large firm tend to have more sophisticated operations and activity than smaller firm (Wafaa Salah 2018).

Firm Leverage

Another factor that can influence Earning management practice is firm leverage. Leverage describes the company's ability with its own capital to guarantee its debt and shows the proportion of company spending that is financed by shareholders (own capital) and the cost of borrowing. Therefore, companies that have high leverage have more obligation to meet the need of adequate information for owners, shareholders and creditors (Jensen and Meckling in Ade Ghofir 2020).

The greater the debt of a company compared to its assets, the greater the risk faced by the company to pay its obligations. The greater the leverage ratio, the greater the level of dependent of the company on external parties (creditors) and the greater the burden of debt costs (interested cost) that must be paid by the company. With the increase in the leverage ratio (where the debt burden is also getting bigger), this will have an impact on the profitability of the company, because part of it is used to pay loan interest (Ade Ghofir 2020).

Firm Age

Firm age is the length of time during which a firm has been officially in existence, the year of incorporation is use as the year of the birth, hence the firm age is the length of the incorporation that is, date of incorporation till date. Prior researches suggest that as a firm grows older many of its features change collectively. These influence number of aspects of its behavior in terms of capital structure decision, there are several studies that document how growth option and so justified their taking on more debt (Sundere Sonetal 2015).

A number of studies have been indicated that firm age is important determination of firm growth, with younger firm grows faster than old firm. Haltiwanger et al (2013) Translated to growth persistence, stated that older firm may have more experience and foresight when it comes to their business environments and can therefore be expected to have smooth growth paths (that is more positive auto related in their growth rate). On the other hand, older firm may suffer from a liability of obsolesce and also a liability of senescence. These emprises lower growth persistence for older firm since they have problem adopting their strategies to change business condition as well as increasing inertia and organizational rigidities. Young firm may also sick to achieve minimum efficient scale as they struggle to overcome their liability of newness achieve economic of scale. However, once they survived first few years and have settle into their new organization routines, growth will lose its momentum (Haltiwanger et al 2013).

Managerial ownership

According to Ali-Momoh et al (2022) Managerial ownership is defined as the percentage of (shares) owned by insiders and block holders, where insiders are the officers and directors of the firm. The separation of ownership and control creates a potential conflict of interest between managers and shareholders. Giving more ownership to managers align their interest with shareholder interests. Mohammad, et al (2018) in Ali-Momoh (2022) defined managerial ownership as a situation where the manager has shares, in other words the manager of the firm as well as the company's shareholders. The definition above looks at the possession of share from an insider perspective, which is not different from the shares held by those at the helm of affairs, i.e. the management of the company. This implies that managerial ownership refers to the number of shares held by those who manage the affairs of the business and act as agents for the public (shareholders), either in naira or in units of shares. As managerial ownership increases, there is a concurrent increase in the alignment of manager and shareholder interests (Dhaliwal, et al 2020).

Income Smoothing

Income smoothing is an attempt to increase the amount of reported profit if actual profit is smaller than normal profit and an attempt to reduce the amount of reported profit if the normal profit is bigger than the actual profit (Oviani 2014) in (Rini Tri Hastuti et al 2021). In simple terms, income smoothing is an action that is intentionally carried out by managers using special tools in accounting to reduce fluctuations in earnings (Bora & Dan Saha, 2015). Income smoothing can be through several dimensions namely: (1) income smoothing through the occurrence or recognition of an event, (2) income smoothing through allocation over a certain period, (3) income smoothing through classification (Rini Tri Hastuti et al 2021). According to Sulistyawan, et al (2011) in Ade Ghofir et al (2020) adapting Scotts' opinion, one of the management actions for earnings that can be taken is income smoothing, income smoothing shows an effort by company management to reduce abnormal variations in earnings within the limits permitted in practice, fair accounting and management principles. If the resulting profit is unstable or continues to fluctuate, then the manager's performance would be questioned and would be bad for the good name of the company. Therefore, managers can do income smoothing to cover up his loophole. Income smoothing is carried out by means of financial engineering which legally and accounting can be justified by taking advantage of weaknesses in accounting standard or applicable rules (Ade Ghofir et al 2020).

Income smoothing aims to stabilize the manager's performance in one period, Company performance includes operating and market performance (Firmansyah & Herawaty, 2019). The income smoothing action is expected to attract investors and potential company investors because the earnings generated by the company are stable (Firmansyah & Herawaty, 2019 & Novianti & Firmansyah, 2020). Income smoothing is not legal if the process follows generally accepted accounting principles (GAAP). Talented accountants are able to adjust financial books in a way to ensure the legality of income smoothing. There are many reasons why a business would want to participate in the smoothing of profits. This could involve reducing taxation, attracting new investors or taking part in a strategic company change. (Will Kenton in Khdiya Khartit 2021).

Theoretical framework

Agency Theory

Agency theory is an economic theory that views the firm as a set of contacts among self-interested individual. An agency relationship is created when a person (the principal) authorized another person (the agent) to act on his or her behalf. This agency theory was independently propounded by Stephen Ross and Barry Mitinick(1973). Shareholder delegated decision making to manager who is compensated for their effort (Jensen and meckling 1976). An agency problem could emerge when a conflict of interest arises where the managers are reluctant to disclose certain information to public - thereby taking advantage of the clarity and fuzzy information about his action to engage in activities or operations to enhance his personal goals and agenda (Ali-Monmoh Oluwayemisi et al 2022).Agency theory states that less concentrated ownership may have incentives for the managers to manipulate the financial numbers for their personal benefit in order to get more earning-based bonuses and less pressure from other shareholders. Past studies have shown that concentrated or blockownership can increase the monitoring effectiveness of the board (Gulzar & Wang, 2011).

Agency theory is related to this study because its focus mainly on extrinsic reward and ignores intrinsic reward like self-interest factors and ethical conduct thereby push the management to smooth earnings to receive such reward of the owners of the firm. That is why it is suggest that fairness is an essential motivator to positive organizational behavior. Also, some people argue that self-interest manager will attempt to maximize their own interest only as long as they are not violating their perceive norms of fairness and reciprocity(Godfrey et al2010 in Arya Pradipta & Yulius 2019).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed *ex-post facto* and descriptive research design. This is because *ex-post facto* research design involves repeated observations of the same units (banks in this study) over a period of time (2013 to 2022). *Ex-post facto* research design also seeks to determine the cause-effect relationship between the dependent and independent variables of the study. Descriptive research was also employed for the purpose of knowing the influence of the various boards attributes on earnings smoothing and which is largely used to draw the inferences about the possible relationship between variables. It is the simplest type of research, which is designed to collect descriptive data and provide information for formulating more sophisticated studies. Furthermore, it involves formulation of more specific hypothesis and testing them through statistical inference.

Area of the study:

The study covered all the quoted deposit money banks firms in Nigeria within the period of ten years from 2013to 2022. We believe that this time period is particularly interesting because it falls within the period at which International Financial Reporting Standard (IFRS) were introduced and fully adopted in the country. The period was adopted to draw a reliable conclusion.

Sources of Data:

This study utilizes secondary data as the main source from the annual report and accounts of the various banks from 2013 to 2022.

Method of Data Collection

These studies make use of secondary data precisely. The data was sourced from publications of the Nigerian Exchange Ltd, fact books, annual report and accounts, and websites of the sample listed banks, particularly the comprehensive income statement and statement of financial positions of these banks as well as their respective notes to the accounts.

Model Specification

This study was adapted the model of Efva, et al (2021): Their original model was stated as follows:

$$EMGT = F(\text{FSIZE, PROF, LEV, AGE})\dots\dots\dots(n)$$

Where

EMGT = Earnings Management (Proxies using accruals)

FSIZE = Firm size (proxies by natural logarithm of total assets)

PROF = Profitability (proxies by return on assets)

LEV = leverage (proxies of debt ratio on total assets)

AGE = Firm age (proxies of date of incorporation till date)

Therefore, our model will adopt the prior studies of Efva et al (2021) whose model was stated above. Therefore, multivariate analysis was used by modeling earnings smoothing (ESMOTH) as a function of explanatory variables. Consistent with previous studies, this model modifies and extends the model tested by Efva et al (2021) and panel least square was adopted for the purpose of hypothesis testing and was guided by the following linear model:

$$Y = F(X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$ESMOTH = (\text{FSIZE} + \text{FLEV} + \text{FAGE} + \text{MOWN} + \dots \dots \dots 1$$

Putting it in testable form, thus we have the testable relationships between the variables as follows:

Follows:

$$ESMOTH = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{FSIZE}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{FLEV}_{it} + \beta_4 \text{FAGE}_{it} + \beta_5 \text{MOWN}_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots 1$$

Where:

ESMOTH stands Earnings Smoothing

FSIZE means Firm Size

FLEV stands for Firms Leverage

FAGE means Firm age,

MOWN connotes Managerial Ownership,

ϵ_{it} = component of unobserved error term of banks i in period t ,

β_0 = constant term, $\beta_1, \beta_2 \dots \beta_4$ = are slopes to be estimated of banks i in period t , i = banks identifier (10 banks), t = time variable (2013, 20142022) – (Ten Years)

Decision Rule:

The degree of the relationship between the dependent and independent variables of this study was determined at 5% level of significance. When the probability value is less than 5% – rejects null hypothesis (H_0) and accepts alternate hypothesis (H_1) but when probability value is greater than 5% – accepts H_0 and rejects H_1 all at 5% level of significance.

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Descriptive statistics was used to discern the pattern of distribution of the data. The use of mean, median, minimum, maximum, count and standard deviation were engaged to understand the data set.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Stats	ES	SIZE	FAGE	FLEV	MOWN
mean	-2.1402	9.426915	26.1	1.839	3.60507
p50	-1.415	9.421289	19	1.695	1.67
min	-17.56	8.809114	8	.48	.02
max	1.35	10.1698	53	4.39	16.75
sd	2.566449	.3306511	15.10535	.8596951	4.343513
N	100	100	100	100	100

Source: Stata 14 output

Normality Test

For the purpose of determining whether or not there are residuals of normality, the assumption that should be made is that the sample distribution is normal. Accordingly, if the test is significant at the 5% or 1% level, the distribution is not normal. In accordance with the viewpoint taken by Razali and Wah (2011), this study used the Shapiro-Wilk test to determine whether or not the residuals were normal. The sample size ranged from ten to two thousand. As a consequence of this, the research attempted to determine whether or not the residuals were normal, as is seen in the table that follows:

Table 2 Shapiro-Wilk W test for Normal Data

Variable	Obs	W	V	z	Prob>z
ES	100	0.68477	26.027	7.230	0.00000
SIZE	100	0.97317	2.215	1.764	0.03885
FAGE	100	0.81514	15.262	6.046	0.00000
FLEV	100	0.94010	4.946	3.546	0.00020
MOWN	100	0.75444	20.275	6.676	0.00000

Source: Stata 14 output

Based on the findings presented on table 2 above, it can be deduced that all the variables have probability values below 5% critical level. Hence, they do not follow a normal distribution. The statistics of probability z, which are presented in the table 4.2 that is located above, are the source of these results. As a result of the research conducted by Bera and Jarque (1982), we provide support for this perspective. Nevertheless, when dealing with non-normal data, as the normalcy of residual test result demonstrates, it is possible that alternative methods to the Pearson correlation approach might be more effectively utilized in the process of assessing the correlations between variables.

Correlation Analysis

There has been less empirical investigation on the robustness of Spearman's test compared to Pearson's test. Fowler (1987) discovered that Spearman's r was more effective than Pearson's r in several non-normal bivariate distributions. Spearman's r may have a power gain due to the rank-ordering process forcing outliers to move closer to the center of the distribution (Gauthier, 2001).

Given the non-normal distribution of our data set, we will use the Spearman Rank Correlation method to analyze the potential relationship between the variables shown in the table below.

Table 3 Correlation Matrix

	ES	SIZE	FAGE	FLEV	MOWN
ES	1.0000				
SIZE	-0.1139	1.0000			
FAGE	0.1239	0.5436*	1.0000		
FLEV	-0.2187*	0.0829	0.0924	1.0000	
MOWN	-0.1342	0.3575*	-0.1804	0.1204	1.0000
	0.1831	0.0003	0.0725	0.2329	

Source: Stata 14 output

Table 4 – Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
SIZE	1.69	0.590467
MOWN	1.45	0.689075
FAGE	1.34	0.748833
FLEV	1.01	0.985719
Mean VIF	1.37	

Source: Stata 14 output

The table 4 above indicates that the average Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is 1.37. VIF's regulation mandates setting a benchmark mean of 10 as the acceptable level. Therefore, a mean VIF above 10 indicates a substantial high correlation among the independent variables. With a result of 1.37, well below the permissible threshold of 10, we may confidently assert the absence of multico linearity in our data.

Constant Variance

Homoscedasticity refers to the expectation that the variance of the error term remains consistent over all observations or a certain range of data. Changes in variance (heteroscedasticity) can decrease the accuracy of estimates in ordinary least square (OLS) linear regression. The study employed the Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test to assess the heteroscedasticity of the residuals, as shown in the table below.

Table 4 Heteroscedasticity Test

Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity

Ho: Constant variance

Variables: fitted values of ES

chi2(1) = 5.74
 Prob > chi2 = 0.0166

Source: Stata 14 output

If the probability of the chi-square value is higher than the critical value at a 5% significance level, the heteroscedasticity test concludes that there is no heteroscedasticity. The table 5 above shows that the probability value of 0.0166 is lower than the crucial threshold of 0.05. Thus, we deduce the presence of heteroscedasticity that amounts to no homoscedasticity, indicating a lack of consistent variation in the error term within the data distribution. The study will apply the use of random effect test for the correction of the heteroscedasticity problem.

Regression Equation Specification Error Test (RESET)

This test evaluates if non-linear combinations of the fitted values contribute to explaining the response variable. If the model fails to account for the potential influence of non-linear combinations of explanatory variables on the response variable, it is considered mis specified. In such cases, the data generating process may be better represented by polynomials or other non-linear functional forms. The study utilized the Ramsey RESET test to examine the existence of non-linear combinations of independent variables, as shown in the table 5 below.

Table 5 Ramsey Reset Test

Ramsey RESET test using powers of the fitted values of ES

Ho: model has no omitted variables

F(3, 92) = 2.26
 Prob > F = 0.0869

Source: Research's Computation (2024)

The outcome of the test for miss-specification or omitted variables, which was carried out with the assistance of the Ramsey RESET Test, is presented in the table 4.6 that is presented above. This test yields a probability value of 0.0869, which indicates that the model contains a combination of linear factors that describe the response variable. The study will also engage the use of random effect test for the correction of the miss specification problem.

Panel Regression Analysis

For the purpose of determining the cause-and-effect relationships that exist between our explanatory factors and the dependent variable, the research utilized panel regression analysis. Additionally, this analysis was utilized for the purpose of evaluating the hypotheses that were developed. The table that follows provides a summary of the findings that were obtained from the panel regression statistical study.

Table 6 – Summary of Panel Regression Analysis

	FEM result	REM result
SIZE	-3.151 (0.049) **	-1.185 (0.004)*
FAGE	.0932 (0.383)	.0196 (0.022)**
FLEV	.0625 (0.652)	-.0839 (0.464)
MOWN	.0015 (0.974)	.0149 (0.606)
R ²	0.3992	0.3180
F	3.49 (0.0109)**	12.17 (0.0161)**
Prob>Chi2 =		0.1564

Researcher's compilation (2024)

- Remarks: (1). *, **, *** means – statistical significance at 10%, 5% and 1% level respectively.
 (2). Brackets () – represents P-values.

Hypotheses Tested

Hypotheses One: firm size has no significant effect on the earnings smoothing of banks in Nigeria.

According to the findings of random effect model test result (REM) shown on Table 7, the coefficient of regression for firm size (SIZE) is -1.185. The fact that this statistic exists suggests that the size of the banks has a negative impact on the earnings smoothing of the deposit money banks in Nigeria. The probability value of 0.000 that is lesser than 5% critical level shows that bank size has statistical significant effect on earnings smoothing (loan loss provision) of the sampled deposit money banks in Nigeria. Hence, the study fails to reject alternate hypotheses which states that bank size has negative and statistical significant effect on earnings smoothing of deposit money banks listed on Nigeria exchange limited.

Hypothesis Two: firm age has no significant effect on the earnings smoothing of banks in Nigeria.

The summarized panel regression result presented on table 7 revealed that the ages of the banks sampled has positive regression coefficient of 0.0196, which indicates that firm age has inverse effect on earnings smoothing of the banks studied. The result depicts that firm age has P-value of 0.022 which implies that, firm age has significant effect on earnings smoothing. Therefore, the study accepts alternate hypothesis and uphold that firm age has positive and statistically significant effect on earnings smoothing of deposit money banks listed on Nigeria exchange limited.

Hypotheses Three: Leverage has no significant effect on the earnings smoothing of banks in Nigeria.

The table more so contains a statistical result that shows Leverage coefficient of -0.0839, which means that, leverage has inverse effect on the earnings smoothing of deposit money banks in Nigeria. Additionally, the table presented statistical evidence that the probability value leverage of 0.464. The probability value suggests that leverage is not significantly determining earnings smoothing of banks. To this the study concludes to accept null hypothesis that leverage has negative and no significant effect on earnings smoothing (loan loss provision) of deposit money banks listed on Nigeria exchange limited.

Hypotheses four: managerial ownership has no significant effect on the earnings smoothing of banks in Nigeria.

The result on table 7 also shows that managerial ownership has regression coefficient of 0.0149 which depict that, managerial ownership has positive effect on earnings smoothing of deposit money banks in Nigeria. Again, the corresponding probability value of 0.606 indicates that managerial ownership has no significant effect on earnings smoothing of the banks. In effect, the study accepts null hypothesis that

insists that managerial ownership has positive and no significant effect on the earnings smoothing (loan loss provision) of the deposit money banks listed on Nigeria exchange limited.

CONCLUSION

The study had successfully undertaken an investigation that empirically x-rayed the effect of firm characteristics on the earnings smoothing of deposit money banks listed on Nigeria Exchange Limited. The study utilized secondary data extracted from annual reports and accounts of the ten sampled banks with specific interest on firm age, firm size, firm leverage and managerial ownership as they affect earnings smoothing. The data mining was for ten years from 2013 to 2022 and robust analytical technique of random effect test was employed for the analysis. The result provided the assurance that forms our conclusion that firm size and firm age are the two veritable firm characteristics that are indispensably determinant of earnings smoothing as measured by loan loss provision of deposit money banks listed on Nigeria Exchange Limited.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Amongst the recommendations is that the regulators should provide specific policy for small sized banks, which should help them establish strategies to efficiently drive their loan policies and collections to reduce the incidence of large outstanding loan loss provision. The regulators should make policy that should assist the newly formed banks manage their loan policies at that early stage of their existence since earnings smoothing (loan loss provision) gets high at the early stages of the banks life. Management should strictly adhere to the leverage level that is equivalent to its optimal capital structure for improved profitability since the leverage position of the banks does not have the capacity to determine its earnings smoothing that was measured with loan loss provision. Management should be at liberty to own any level of shares of the enterprise since managerial ownership has no impact on loan loss provision, although the more ownership they have the larger shares of the company they bought shows signs of reduced earnings smoothing.

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